

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R5.2 Report and dataset: Chemistry of fluids

Authors: Juraj Franců, Daniela Ocásková, Petr Pařízek,
Miroslav Pereszlényi, František Bůzek, Bohuslava Čejková,
Petr Jirman, Blanka Janíková (CGS),
Štěpán Káňa, Vladimír Opletal (MND),
Monika Ličbinská, Martin Klempa (VŠB)

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1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this report in Work Package 5 is to provide information about composition and properties of formation fluids, i.e. oil, gas and water.

The oil analytical results include:

- Standard oil parameters
- Molecular fingerprints and type of oil
- Thermal maturity of oil;
- Co-sourcing and mixing of heavy and light oil fractions
- Biodegradation of oil
- Water washing of oil in reservoir.

The gas analytical results include:

- Detailed chemical composition focussed on methane and CO₂
- Gas typing
- Thermal maturity
- Microbiological effects
- Mixing and migration alterations
- H₂S occurrence and risk assessment.

Formation water analytical data include information on:

- Sampling depth, pressure and temperature;
- pH, Eh, conductivity;
- Mineralization, i.e. total dissolved solids (TDS);
- Ionic compositions of formation water

Results of T5.1 are intended to be used in the evaluation of fluids miscibility, CO₂ dissolution, phase equilibria and simulation of fluid flow in the reservoir within dynamic modelling in WP3 and in other Tasks of WP4 and WP5, such as in experiments on fluid-rock interactions. The results are summarised in this report and dataset is stored in the project geodatabase.

2 SAMPLING SITES

2.1 Oil samples

Oil samples were collected at the following sites shown in Fig. 2-1. The coordinates, measured depth, stratigraphy and lithostratigraphic units are listed in Tab. 2-1.

Fig. 2-1: Reference oil sample locations in the adjacent oil & gas fields listed in Tab. 1.

Tab. 2-1: List of Zar-3 and reference oil samples used in this study

Lab No.	Locality	Well-No.	M. Depth 1 (m)	M. Depth 2 (m)	Sampling date	Stratigraphy	Litostratigraphy
2130467	Borkovany	Bor-1	2092	2051	30.6.21	L. Eocene	Těšany Fm.
2130468	Borkovany	Bor-2	2660	2633	30.6.21	Paleogene	Těšany Fm.
2130469	Borkovany	Bor-3	2155	2127	30.6.21	L. Eocene	Těšany Fm.
2130470	Borkovany	Bor-4	2337	2305	30.6.21	Paleogene	Těšany Fm.
2130471	Bošovice	Boš-103	1760	1741	30.6.21	M. Eocene	Těšany Fm.
15340	Karlín	KA1	3930	3914	24.4.95	M. Eocene	Těšany Fm.
2130447	Kobeřice	Kob-101	1368	1360	1.12.21	Jurassic	Gresten Fm.
2130448	Krumvíř	Kru-2	3256,2	3252	26.7.01	Eocene	bazální sv.
2130449	Nikolčice	Nik-2A	1221	1201	28.4.80	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2130451	Uhřice	Uh-102	1735	1717	1.12.21	M. Jurassic	Gresten Fm.
2130452	Uhřice	Uh-16	2452	2443	20.8.87	Devonian	Lažánky Fm.
2130454	Uhřice	Uh-19	2836	2829	30.4.86	U. Jurassic	Mikulov Fm.
2130455	Uhřice	Uh-2	2505	2480	28.4.80	U. Carboniferous	Ostrava Fm.
9487	Uhřice	UH3	1650	1640	9.9.86	U. Jurassic	Mikulov Fm.
2130456	Uhřice	Uh-22	1575	1563	13.6.86	M. Jurassic	Gresten Fm.
2130476	Uhřice	Uh-102	1735	1712	30.6.21	M. Jurassic	Gresten Fm.
2130472	Uhřice	Uh-49	1673	1652	30.6.21	M. Jurassic	Gresten Fm.
2130473	Uhřice	Uh-57	1923	1919	30.6.21	M. Jurassic	Gresten Fm.
2130474	Uhřice	Uh-64	1899	1897	30.6.21	M. Jurassic	Gresten Fm.
2130475	Uhřice	Uh-86	1686	1673	30.6.21	M. Jurassic	Gresten Fm.
2842\2001	Žarošice	ZA3	1 810	1 741	17.9.01	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2130406	Žarošice	ZA4a	1842	1802,5	14.7.21	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2835\2003	Žarošice	ZA5H	2860	2550,15	20.8.03	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
3260\2011	Žarošice	ZA6a	2000	1898,89	19.7.11	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2220147	Žarošice	ZA8aH	2440	2338	17.5.22	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
4418\2004	Žarošice	ZA9aH	2475	2201,6	27.12.04	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
6652\2016	Žarošice	ZA14H	2255	2116,5	24.11.16	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2130453	Ždánice	Zd-15	941	895	5.2.93	crystalline	basement
2140689	Ždánice	Zd-52	948,5	939,5	1.12.21	L. Miocene	Karpatian
2140690	Ždánice	Zd-146	927	908	1.12.21	L. Miocene	Karpatian
2140691	Ždánice	Zd-173	855	847	1.12.21	L. Miocene	Karpatian

2.2 Gas samples

Gas samples were collected at the following wells on the specified date (Tab. 2-2).

Tab. 2-2. Zar-3 and reference gas samples

Sample No.	Well ZA-No.	Sampling date	Sampling details	Depth 1 (m)	Depth 2 (m)	Stratigr. age	Litho-stratigraphy
147\2002	3	16.1.02	through separator	1740	1780	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
436\2002	3	7.2.02	through separator	1740	1780	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2024\2002	4A	11.6.02	through separator	1802	1842	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
1562\2003	4A	15.5.03	through separator	1802	1842	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
3232\2018	4A	5.6.18	from annulus	1802	1842	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
978\2010	5H	5.3.10	through separator	2550	2860	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2896\2003	6a	26.8.03	at well head	1899	2000	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2668\2015	8AH	28.4.15	from tubing at well head	2338	2440	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2669\2015	8AH	28.4.15	from annulus at well head	2338	2440	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
4419\2004	9AH	27.12.04	through separator	2202	2475	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
3233\2018	14H	5.6.18	at well head	2117	2255	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.

2.3 Water samples

List of formation water samples is in Tab. 2-3.

Tab. 2-3: Zar-3 and reference formation water samples

Sample Lab No.	Well-No.	M. Depth 1 (m)	M. Depth 2 (m)	Sampling date	Stratigraphy	Lithostratigraphy
1524\2012	ZA4a	1842	1802,5	17.5.22	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
6680\2015	ZA5AH	2860	2550,15	7.7.05	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
2301\2015	ZA8AH	2440	2338	1.6.14	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
3029\2016	ZA8AH	2440	2338	1.6.14	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.
1524\2013	ZA8AH	2440	2338	17.5.22	U. Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Oil analysis

Standard oil analyses

Oils were analysed using standard petrochemical analysis, such as determination of density, viscosity, distillation fractures and sulphur content (MND laboratory).

Determination of density of liquids – by oscillating U-tube method and calculation of API gravity index - ČSN EN ISO 12185

Determination of distillation characteristics at atmospheric pressure - ČSN EN ISO 3405; ČSN EN ISO 4264

Determination of water content by KF method by volumetry - ČSN ISO 760

Determination of flash point – Pensky-Martens closed cup - ČSN EN ISO 2719 procedure A, C

Determination of dynamic viscosity by falling-ball viscometer and calculation of kinematic viscosity and viscosity index - ČSN EN ISO 3104; ČSN ISO 2909;

Determination of acid value by potentiometry - ČSN EN 12634

Determination of elements by ED XRF - ČSN EN ISO 8754; ČSN EN ISO 20847; ČSN EN ISO 13032; ASTM D8252

Whole oil and light hydrocarbon analysis

Unfractionated whole oil was analysed using gas chromatography with flame ionisation detector (FID). Identification of gasoline range light hydrocarbons C₅-C₁₃ was based on literature data and a reference North Sea Oil purchased from the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate.

Chromatography of n-alkanes and biomarkers

Rock samples were extracted by DIONEX accelerated (high pressure) method. Saturated (SAT) and aromatic (ARO) hydrocarbon fractions of oils and extracts were prepared and separated from polar fraction using silicagel column chromatography. Gas chromatography with flame ionisation detection (GC-FID) and mass selective detection (GC-MS) were used for analysis of the saturate and aromatic fractions of oils and extracts. Identification of compounds was made using mass spectra libraries and a reference North Sea Oil purchased from the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate.

3.2 Gas analysis

Chemical composition of gas

Gas was collected from the production wells and soil probes was analysed using gas chromatography equipped with thermal conductivity and flame ionisation detectors (GC-TCD-FID).

Isotopic composition of carbon and hydrogen

Isotopic composition of carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and hydrogen (δD) was analysed using isotopic ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS).

3.3 Water analysis

Chemical composition of water

Chemical composition of water was analysed using FAAS, ICP-MS, HPLC and titration.

3.4 Statistical methods

Multivariate statistical analysis includes cluster analysis using MVSP and PAST software (Hammer et al. 2001).

4 RESULTS

4.1 Oil composition

Oils analytical data are presented in Tabs. 4-1 to 4-21.

Archival data of standard oil analysis carried out routinely in the MND laboratories are shown in Tabs. 4-10. Distillation fractions show the proportions of light and heavy hydrocarbons, polars and asphatenes.

Light gasoline range hydrocarbons are studied in detail using the whole oil analysis carried out at the Czech Geological Survey. The results are shown in context of the mixture of gasoline and black oil, which are often of very different origin.

Biomarkers are mostly polycyclic saturated and aromatic compounds. They are used by most international oil companies for the purposes of oils-source rock and oil-oil correlations, grouping of oils into families and characterising thermal maturity of oils in respect to source rocks in the studied basins.

Tab. 4-1: Archival standard analyses of oil samples from Žarošice field (MND)

ZA-well #		ZA3	ZA3	ZA4A	ZA5H	ZA5H	ZA6A
Measured Depth 1	m	1740.5	1740.5	1802.3	2550.2	2550.2	1898.9
Measured Depth 2	m	1780	1780	1842	2860	2860	2000
MND No.		2425\ 2001	2842\ 2001	1941\ 2002	2835\ 2003	6657\ 2015	2897\ 2003
Sampling date		8.8.01	17.9.01	31.5.02	20.8.03	7.7.05	26.8.03
Density at 15°C	kg/m ³	909.6	906.7	910.7	910.6	916.1	911.8
API	°	23.98	24.48	23.80	23.75	22.87	23.55
Dyn. viscosity at 20°C	mPa.s	19.40	39.90	57.10	40.5	51.8	44.7
Parafinns	% mass	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.8	1.1
Sulphur	% mass	-	-	0.160	0.154	0.147	0.155
Aromatic HC - CA	% mass	17	28	17	16	18	16
Naphthenic HC - CN	% mass	39	17	38	39	42	39
Parafinic HC - CP	% mass	44	55	45	45	40	45
Vanadium V	mg/kg					0.38	
Nickel Ni	mg/kg					1.71	
Acidity number	mg KOH/g	0.46	1.04	0.98	0.77	0.625	710.00
Ignition point PM	°C	16.00		14.50	12.50	48	32.00
Water content, KF	% mass	0.70		0.30	1.40	21.0	27.90
Mech. impurities	% mass	0.10	0.10	<0.100	0.03	0.0818	0.01
Asphalt-resins	% vol	18.00	14.40	17.20	16.80	14.5	14.80
Solidification point	°C	<-30	<-30	<-30	<-30	<-30	<-30
Distillation start, IBP	°C	99	97	122	107	170	110
10 % vol	°C	227	233	244	244	263	242
20 % vol.	°C	270	268	280	279	294	303
30 % vol.	°C	299	299	307	306	330	331
40 % vol.	°C	327	327	336	335		357
Start-200°C dist. fract.	% vol	6	5	4	4	1	4
200°C-300°C	% vol	24	25	24	24	21	24
300°-350°C	% vol	17	17	17	17	14	18
350°C & more	% vol	53	53	55	55	64	
Refraction index		1.501	1.510	1.502	1.501	1.504	1.502
Cryo. mol. mass	g/mol	290	292	296	307	279	308

Tab. 4-2: Archival standard analyses of oil samples from Žarošice field (MND)

ZA-well #		ZA6A	ZA8AH	ZA8AH	ZA8AH	ZA9AH	ZA14H
Measured Depth 1	m	1896.9	2338.0	2338.0	2338.0	2201.6	2116.5
Measured Depth 2	m	2000	2440	2440	2440	2475	2255
MND No.		3260\ 2011	3333\ 2014	3410\ 2014	2295\ 2015	4418\ 2004	6652\ 2016
Sampling date		19.7.11	23.6.14	24.6.14	9.4.15	27.12.04	24.11.16
Density at 15°C	kg/m ³	909.7	915.3	914.8	900.5	911.6	913.6
API	°	23.95	23.00	23.09	25.54	23.58	23.29
Dyn. viscosity at 20°C	mPa.s	34.3	39.4	39.6	32.7	46.15	46.7
Parafinns	% mass	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.4	0.7
Sulphur	% mass	0.128	0.159	0.146	0.154	0.145	0.153
Aromatic HC - CA	% mass	18	12	14	19	20	18
Naphthenic HC - CN	% mass	37	50	47	32	33	37
Parafinic HC - CP	% mass	45	37	39	49	47	46
Vanadium V	mg/kg	0.52	0.45	0.07	0.10	<2.00	0.13
Nickel Ni	mg/kg	2.84	5.03	3.32	1.79	2.52	1.93
Acidity number	mg KOH/g	0.843	0.028	0.015	0.518	0.740	0.646
Ignition point PM	°C	-3	49	54	<20	16	16
Water content, KF	% mass	2.50	3.17	2.02	59.5	0.023	24.5
Mech. impurities	% mass	0.0202	0.0142	0.0138	0.0166	<0.002	0.0478
Asphalt-resins	% vol	14.0	16.5	16.5	17.5	11.5	16.5
Solidification point	°C	<-30	<-30	<-30	<-30	<-45	<-30
Distillation start, IBP	°C	73	84	74	69	123	
10 % vol.	°C	218	270	274	216	244	
20 % vol.	°C	268	311	312	269	278	
30 % vol.	°C	290	352	349	303	304	
40 % vol.	°C	320			337	332	
Start-200°C dist. fract.	% vol	8	1	1	8		
200°C-300°C	% vol	26	17	16	21	25	
300°-350°C	% vol	13	11	13	15	18	
350°C & more	% vol	53	71	70	56	53	
Refraction index		1.502	1.499	1.500	1.499	1.505	1.504
Cryo. mol. mass	g/mol	293	288	292	281	297	309

Tab. 4-3: Archival standard analyses of oil samples from neighbouring fields (MND)

ZA-well #		KRU2A	NIK2A	UH2	UH3	UH16
Measured Depth 1	m	3252	1202	2505	1640	2443
Measured Depth 2	m	3256,5	1209	2483	1650	2452
MND No.		1027\	6955\	499\	383\	8920\
MND year		2000	1974	1992	1978	1991
Sampling date		24.5.00	8.8.74	7.9.92	6.6.78	16.7.91
Density at 15°C	kg/m ³	803	858,9	831,8	938,7	879,8
API	°	44,6	33,1665	38,53414	19,1615	29,25284
Dyn. viscosity at 20°C	mPa.s	1,26	5,65	-	201,64	-
Parafinns	% mass	1,7	0,27	3,3	1,83	10
Sulphur	% mass	0,1	-	-	-	-
Aromatic HC - CA	% mass	14	12,6	21,2	12,5	19,1
Naphthenic HC - CN	% mass	15	39,1	7,6	51,8	45,1
Parafinic HC - CP	% mass	71	48,3	71,1	35,7	35,7
Vanadium V	mg/kg	-	-	-	-	-
Nickel Ni	mg/kg	-	-	-	-	-
Acidity number	mg KOH/g	0,02	0,08	<0,01	1,25	0,1
Ignition point PM	°C	<-40	15	-37	30	28
Water content, KF	% mass	<0.1	7,4	<0,1	55	0,9
Mech. impurities	% mass	<0.1	<0,1	<0,1	0,2	0,4
Asphalt-resins	% vol	5,2	6,8	4,8	24	13,2
Solidification point	°C	<-40	<-40	13	<-40	8
Distillation start, IBP	°C	54	104	48	198	92
10 % vol	°C	109	152	107	174	216
20 % vol.	°C	121	182	137	326	268
30 % vol.	°C	135	219	177	357	299
40 % vol.	°C	152	254	229	360	326
50 % vol	°C	176	290	274	-	360
60 % vol	°C	204	327	306	-	-
70 % vol	°C	246	360	342	-	-
80 % vol	°C	326	-	363	-	-
Final boiling pt. FBP	°C	-	-	-	-	-
Start-200°C dist. fract.	% vol	59	25	34,5	0,5	8
200°C-300°C	% vol	19	28	24	15	23
300°-350°C	% vol	22	14	16	13	17
350°C & more	% vol	-	34	26	72	52
Refraction index		1,45	1,474	1,469	1,5107	1,485
Cryo. mol. mass	g/mol	167	212	204	361	190

Tab. 4-4: Archival standard analyses of oil samples from neighbouring fields (MND)

ZA-well #		UH19	ZD15	BOR1	BOR2	BOR3
Measured Depth 1	m	2836	895	2051	2634	2128
Measured Depth 2	m	2829	941	2092	2661	2155
MND No.		5284\	3374\	1951\	4327\	4328\
MND year		1986	1983	2017	2019	2019
Sampling date		30.4.86	17.8.83	10.4.17	24.8.19	24.8.19
Density at 15°C	kg/m ³	880,6	883,8	852,2	878,4	849,1
API	°	29,11	28,52	34,46	29,5	35,05
Dyn. viscosity at 20°C	mPa.s	-	17,7	8,51	108	8,66
Paraffins	% mass	5,16	1,78	2,8	5,1	4,3
Sulphur	% mass	-	-	0,076	0,138	0,104
Aromatic HC - CA	% mass	14,2	15,0	18,0	20,0	17,0
Naphthenic HC - CN	% mass	30,3	30,4	23,0	39,0	22,0
Parafinic HC - CP	% mass	55,5	54,6	60,0	42,0	61,0
Vanadium V	mg/kg	-	-	0,26	0,17	<0,05
Nickel Ni	mg/kg	-	-	1,78	3,01	1,34
Acidity number	mg KOH/g	0,1	0,56	0,319	0,42	0,338
Ignition point PM	°C	26	10	<20	<25	<25
Water content, KF	% mass	35	<0,1	0,337	2,17	0,112
Mech. impurities	% mass	12	<0,1	0,0124	0,0283	0,0195
Asphalt-resins	% vol	16	18,4	14	23,6	21,2
Solidification point	°C	1	<-40	5	17	8
Distillation start, IBP	°C	81	73	67	----- 16)	52
10 % vol	°C	157	159	152	----- 16)	146
20 % vol.	°C	217	228	207	-	201
30 % vol.	°C	257	269	249	-	247
40 % vol.	°C	287	305	284	-	283
50 % vol	°C	317	336	318	-	316
60 % vol	°C	341	350	-	-	-
70 % vol	°C	350	-	-	-	-
80 % vol	°C	-	-	-	-	-
Final boiling pt. FBP	°C	-	-	-	-	-
Start-200°C dist. fract.	% vol	17	16	19	-	20
200°C-300°C	% vol	27	23	26	-	25
300°-350°C	% vol	20	17	14	-	14
350°C & more	% vol	36	45	41	-	41
Refraction index		1,487	1,489	1,476	1,486	1,474
Cryo. mol. mass	g/mol	294	293	235	204	236

Tab. 4-5: Archival standard analyses of oil samples from neighbouring fields (MND)

ZA-well #		BOR4	BOŠ103	KAR1	Kob101	Uh102
Measured Depth 1	m	2322	1742	3914	1360	1698
Measured Depth 2	m	2371	1760	3930	1368	1712
MND No.		1250\	5078\	2994\	3165\	7204\
MND year		2021	2017	2008	2007	2017
Sampling date		11.3.21	6.9.17	2.8.08	28.6.07	18.12.17
Density at 15°C	kg/m ³	891,6	914,1	794,4	941,1	868,7
API	°	27,12	23,21	46,47	18,72	31,31
Dyn. viscosity at 20°C	mPa.s	24,04	63,6	1,09	495	18
Paraffins	% mass	4	1,2	0,4	1,5	4,7
Sulphur	% mass	0,143	0,176	0,023	0,208	0,128
Aromatic HC - CA	% mass	15,0	15,0	18,3	2,0	17,0
Naphthenic HC - CN	% mass	64,0	41,0	4,8	62,0	34,0
Parafinic HC - CP	% mass	21,0	43,0	76,9	36,0	49,0
Vanadium V	mg/kg	0,39	0,15	0,66	0,92	0,29
Nickel Ni	mg/kg	4,17	4,04	2,61	6,5	2,65
Acidity number	mg KOH/g	0,518	1,018	0,014	0,485	0,519
Ignition point PM	°C	----- 16)	-	< -40	75	<25
Water content, KF	% mass	44	3,03	0,07	27,4	16
Mech. impurities	% mass	0,0212	0,0416	<0,002	0,062	0,0173
Asphalt-resins	% vol	14,8	21,6	10,4	37,5	11,6
Solidification point	°C	-13	<-30	-36	-28	-6
Distillation start, IBP	°C	126	118	49	251	79
10 % vol	°C	220,3	250	77	307	160
20 % vol.	°C	254,9	283	110	340	224
30 % vol.	°C	285,2	316	127	360	273
40 % vol.	°C	311,8	353	148	-	308
50 % vol	°C	344,3	-	178	-	342
60 % vol	°C	374,8	-	216	-	-
70 % vol	°C	408	-	251	-	-
80 % vol	°C	441	-	284	-	-
Final boiling pt. FBP	°C	511,5	-	300	-	-
Start-200°C dist. fract.	% vol	7	2	70	0	16
200°C-300°C	% vol	29	23	20	9	22
300°C-350°C	% vol	16	14	8	15	15
350°C & more	% vol	48	61	2	76	47
Refraction index		1,486	1,502	1,449	1,515	1,481
Cryo. mol. mass	g/mol	171	308	139	343	222

Tab. 4-6: Archival standard analyses of oil samples from neighbouring fields (MND)

ZA-well #		Uh22	Uh49	Uh57	Uh64	Uh86
Measured Depth 1	m	1566	1673	1920	1881	1673
Measured Depth 2	m	1566	1680	1920	1889	1687,8
MND No.		3464\	1381\	5610\	1250\	4251\
MND year		2015	2016	2015	2013	2017
Sampling date		14.6.15	26.2.16	8.10.15	7.3.13	20.7.17
Density at 15°C	kg/m ³	861,6	862,5	903,6	908,5	871,6
API	°	32,65	32,46	25,01	24,15	30,75
Dyn. viscosity at 20°C	mPa.s	13,8	11,5	48,5	48,2	37,9
Paraffins	% mass	1,3	3,1	2,6	2	4,7
Sulphur	% mass	0,122	0,115	0,203	0,188	0,135
Aromatic HC - CA	% mass	18,0	20,0	19,0	17,0	14,0
Naphthenic HC - CN	% mass	23,0	23,0	31,0	40,0	37,0
Parafinic HC - CP	% mass	59,0	57,0	51,0	43,0	49,0
Vanadium V	mg/kg	0,14	0,44	0,6	0,56	0,29
Nickel Ni	mg/kg	1,78	1,44	2,81	5,24	2,62
Acidity number	mg KOH/g	0,306	0,193	2,281	2,4	0,573
Ignition point PM	°C	<20	<15	<20	-----16)	<20
Water content, KF	% mass	3,38	13,0	0,118	6,72	2,51
Mech. impurities	% mass	0,0172	0,0611	0,0142	0,0216	0,0216
Asphalt-resins	% vol	15,6	12,8	23	24	12,4
Solidification point	°C	-8	3	<-30	<-30	14
Distillation start, IBP	°C	68	72	70	65	86
10 % vol	°C	161	155	193	238	174
20 % vol.	°C	234	218	260	287	254
30 % vol.	°C	284	265	303	328	300
40 % vol.	°C	325	305	343	-	341
50 % vol	°C	-	337	-	-	-
60 % vol	°C	-	-	-	-	-
70 % vol	°C	-	-	-	-	-
80 % vol	°C	-	-	-	-	-
Final boiling pt. FBP	°C	-	-	-	-	-
Start-200°C dist. fract.	% vol	15	17	11	5	13
200°C-300°C	% vol	19	22	18	18	17
300°-350°C	% vol	13	15	13	13	12
350°C & more	% vol	53	46	58	64	58
Refraction index		1,481	1,482	1,501	1,5	1,481
Cryo. mol. mass	g/mol	248	235	305	285	236

Tab. 4-7: Archival standard analyses of oil samples from neighbouring fields (MND)

ZA-well #		ZA4a	ZA8AH	Zd52	Zd146	Zd173
Measured Depth 1	m	1802,25	2338	939,5	908	847
Measured Depth 2	m	1842	2440	948,5	927	588
MND No.		1941\	2295\	3057\	3341\	1339\
MND year		2002	2015	2004	2008	2023
Sampling date		31.5.02	9.4.15	24.9.04	29.8.08	14.3.23
Density at 15°C	kg/m ³	907,2	900,5	886,7	949,4	953
API	°	23,8	25,54	27,93	17,41	16,88
Dyn. viscosity at 20°C	mPa.s	51,7	32,7	25,78	726	792,9
Paraffins	% mass	0,6	0,9	5,3	1,8	0,7
Sulphur	% mass	0,16	0,154	0,094	0,251	0,196
Aromatic HC - CA	% mass	17,0	19,0	17,0	24,0	18,0
Naphthenic HC - CN	% mass	38,0	32,0	28,0	35,0	52,0
Parafinic HC - CP	% mass	45,0	49,0	55,0	41,0	30,0
Vanadium V	mg/kg	-	0,1	5,59	1,06	<1,5
Nickel Ni	mg/kg	-	1,79	7	15,9	6,7
Acidity number	mg KOH/g	0,98	0,518	0,58	2,479	2,45
Ignition point PM	°C	14,5	<20	-16	121	-
Water content, KF	% mass	0,3	59,5	0,704	1,63	18,4
Mech. impurities	% mass	<0,1	0,0166	0,103	0,091	0,3384
Asphalt-resins	% vol	17,2	17,5	20,4	29,6	23
Solidification point	°C	<-30	<-30	-10	<-30	-27
Distillation start, IBP	°C	122	69	69	227	126
10 % vol	°C	244	216	183	300	232,8
20 % vol.	°C	280	269	247	338	268,1
30 % vol.	°C	307	303	285	361	295,6
40 % vol.	°C	336	337	319	-	323,8
50 % vol	°C	-	-	350	-	354,4
60 % vol	°C	-	-	-	-	384,3
70 % vol	°C	-	-	-	-	412,1
80 % vol	°C	-	-	-	-	442,3
Final boiling pt. FBP	°C	-	-	-	-	-
Start-200°C dist. fract.	% vol	4	8	12	1	4
200°C-300°C	% vol	24	21	22	9	27
300°-350°C	% vol	17	15	16	14	17
350°C & more	% vol	55	56	50	76	>48
Refraction index		1,502	1,499	1,492	1,526	1,52
Cryo. mol. mass	g/mol	-	281	290	362	-

Saturated and aromatic hydrocarbon, polar and asphaltene fractions of oils are presented quantitatively in Tab. 4-8.

Tab. 4-8: Saturate (aliphatic), aromatic, polar and asphaltene fractions of selected oils

#	Sample lab No.	Well-No.	Saturates (%m)	Aromatics (%m)	Polars (%m)	Asphaltenes (%m)	Sum (%m)
1	2130406	ZA4a	42,4	23,9	3,4	30,3	100
2	2130467	Bor-1	50,5	16,7	2,8	30,0	100
3	2130468	Bor-2	47,9	19,2	2,6	30,3	100
4	2130469	Bor-3	45,6	15,2	2,3	36,9	100
5	2130470	Bor-4	47,0	14,3	2,1	36,6	100
6	2130457	Bos103	60,2	19,7	4,3	15,7	100
7	2130471	Bos-103	42,7	26,4	4,6	26,3	100
8	2130447	Kob-101	58,2	24,3	3,3	14,2	100
9	2130448	Kru-2	65,1	28,2	3,9	2,7	100
10	2130449	Nik-2A	61,9	27,8	7,2	3,1	100
11	2130450	NP-360	57,1	22,0	2,4	18,5	100
12	2130451	Uh-102	62,0	25,0	3,3	9,7	100
13	2130476	Uh-102	47,9	17,4	3,1	31,6	100
14	2130452	Uh-16	71,2	19,2	3,8	5,8	100
15	2130454	Uh-19	55,0	32,2	4,6	8,3	100
16	2130455	Uh-2	62,8	23,0	3,9	10,3	100
17	2130456	Uh-22	69,7	18,7	3,2	8,4	100
18	2130472	Uh-49	49,6	19,6	3,2	27,7	100
19	2130473	Uh-57	37,4	25,5	5,1	32,0	100
20	2130474	Uh-64	39,1	25,4	5,2	30,3	100
21	2130475	Uh-86	48,2	18,4	2,9	30,5	100
22	2130453	Zd-15	74,3	18,5	3,5	3,7	100

Saturated hydrocarbons prevail in oils generated from kerogen at higher temperatures, such as 90-150°C (Hunt 19). They are usually the first ones to be removed by bacterial biodegradation in the reservoir at temperature below 65 °C . Aromatic hydrocarbons are preferentially being removed from the reservoir by water washing. Polar and asphaltene fractions increase in the residual oil accumulations with biodegradation.

Tab. 4-9: Gasoline range light hydrocarbons in oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Sample number	Well Name- No.	Depth (m)	Litho stratigraphy Fm.	UCM rel (%)	% Hept +2,4DMP Star Diagram Ratios		
					% Hept Halpern	%2,3DMP	%Tol
2130406	Za4a_1	1802	Vranovice	77,7	27,06	41,00	31,94
2130467	Bor-1	2051	Těšany	41,7	44,75	8,95	46,30
2130468	Bor-2	2633	Těšany	49,1	58,03	9,77	32,21
2130469	Bor-3	2127	Těšany	41,8	45,79	9,00	45,21
2130457	Bos103	1741	Těšany	42,4	39,97	6,14	53,89
2130471	Bos-103	1741	Těšany	78,9	47,41	12,10	40,49
2130470	Bos-4	2305	Těšany	44,2	48,65	9,56	41,79
2130447	Kob-101	1360	Gresten	54,4	36,61	5,70	57,69
2130448	Kru-2	3252	Těšany	39,6	45,04	24,13	30,83
2130449	Nik-2A	1201	Vranovice	50,3	59,91	35,20	4,88
2130451	Uh-102	1717	Gresten	44,8	40,41	7,59	51,99
2130452	Uh-16	2443	Devonian	46,8	40,83	5,24	53,92
2130454	Uh-19	2829	Mikulov	80,6	41,29	48,76	9,95
2130455	Uh-2	2480	Ostrava	46,7	32,58	5,24	62,19
2130456	Uh-22	1563	Gresten	36,4	6,57	22,74	70,69
2130476	Uhr-102	1712	Gresten	45,3	49,25	11,01	39,73
2130472	Uhr-49	1652	Gresten	46,5	48,37	11,38	40,25
2130473	Uhr-57	1919	Gresten	74,6	63,52	12,26	24,22
2130474	Uhr-64	1897	Gresten	67,5	61,79	11,46	26,75
2130475	Uhr-86	1673	Gresten	43,8	48,44	8,91	42,65
2130453	Zda-15	895	crystalline	31,0	73,67	8,74	17,59

Tab. 4-10: Gasoline range light hydrocarbons in oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Sample number	Well Name- No.	Tr1	Tr2	Tr3	Tr4
		<u>Tol</u> 1,1-DMCP	<u>nC7</u> 1,1-DMCP	<u>3MH</u> 1,1-DMCP	<u>2MH</u> 1,1-DMCP
		Transformation Ratios Halpern		Star Diagram	Ratios
2130406	Za4a_1	1.27	1.08	0.89	0.62
2130467	Bor-1	11.08	10.71	4.06	4.01
2130468	Bor-2	7.56	13.63	4.82	4.57
2130469	Bor-3	10.26	10.39	3.95	3.95
2130457	Bos103	19.21	14.25	4.81	4.77
2130471	Bos-103	7.56	8.86	3.48	3.40
2130470	Bos-4	9.26	10.78	4.18	4.06
2130447	Kob-101	21.46	13.62	5.00	4.51
2130448	Kru-2	2.39	3.49	2.54	2.26
2130449	Nik-2A	1.26	15.50	4.11	2.99
2130451	Uh-102	15.50	12.04	4.98	4.87
2130452	Uh-16	19.47	14.74	4.75	4.66
2130454	Uh-19	0.48	1.98	1.67	2.01
2130455	Uh-2	22.70	11.89	4.48	4.60
2130456	Uh-22	1.13	0.11	3.08	0.08
2130476	Uhr-102	7.59	9.41	4.17	4.01
2130472	Uhr-49	7.01	8.42	3.95	3.86
2130473	Uhr-57	4.49	11.77	4.47	4.16
2130474	Uhr-64	5.53	12.77	4.81	4.43
2130475	Uhr-86	10.23	11.62	4.53	4.43
2130453	Zda-15	4.87	20.40	6.41	6.25

Tab. 4-11: Gasoline range light hydrocarbons in oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Sample number	Well Name- No.	Tr5	Tr6	Tr7	Tr8
		<u>P2</u> 1,1-DMCP TR Halpern	<u>1c2-DMCP</u> 1,1-DMCP light end loss Star Diagram	<u>1t3-DMCP</u> 1,1-DMCP Transformation Ratios	<u>P2</u> P3
2130406	Za4a_1	1.50	0.00	0.78	0.70
2130467	Bor-1	8.07	0.00	1.77	2.87
2130468	Bor-2	9.39	0.00	2.01	3.29
2130469	Bor-3	7.90	0.00	1.76	2.90
2130457	Bos103	9.57	0.00	1.97	3.37
2130471	Bos-103	6.88	0.00	1.71	2.32
2130470	Bos-4	8.24	0.00	1.90	2.98
2130447	Kob-101	9.51	0.00	2.14	3.55
2130448	Kru-2	4.80	0.00	1.16	1.84
2130449	Nik-2A	7.10	0.00	0.71	0.59
2130451	Uh-102	9.85	0.00	2.02	3.42
2130452	Uh-16	9.40	0.00	1.59	3.61
2130454	Uh-19	3.68	0.00	1.59	0.90
2130455	Uh-2	9.09	0.00	1.41	3.22
2130456	Uh-22	3.16	0.00	0.13	5.26
2130476	Uhr-102	8.18	0.00	1.70	2.99
2130472	Uhr-49	7.81	0.00	1.60	2.91
2130473	Uhr-57	8.64	0.00	1.99	3.03
2130474	Uhr-64	9.24	0.00	2.02	3.08
2130475	Uhr-86	8.97	0.00	1.83	3.22
2130453	Zda-15	12.66	0.00	2.10	4.04

Tab. 4-12: Gasoline range light hydrocarbons in oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Sample number	Well Name-No.	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
		2,2-DMP P3	2,3-DMP P3	2,4-DMP P3	3,3-DMP P3	3-EP P3
		Correlation Ratios				light end loss
		Halpern Star Diagram Ratios				
2130406	Za4a_1	0.12	0.55	0.20	0.12	0
2130467	Bor-1	0.13	0.51	0.25	0.11	0
2130468	Bor-2	0.11	0.55	0.25	0.08	0
2130469	Bor-3	0.14	0.51	0.24	0.11	0
2130457	Bos103	0.13	0.52	0.25	0.10	0
2130471	Bos-103	0.13	0.51	0.25	0.11	0
2130470	Bos-4	0.13	0.53	0.24	0.11	0
2130447	Kob-101	0.10	0.60	0.20	0.11	0
2130448	Kru-2	0.15	0.51	0.20	0.13	0
2130449	Nik-2A	0.07	0.31	0.45	0.18	0
2130451	Uh-102	0.12	0.53	0.25	0.09	0
2130452	Uh-16	0.14	0.50	0.22	0.14	0
2130454	Uh-19	0.13	0.33	0.24	0.29	0
2130455	Uh-2	0.17	0.43	0.25	0.15	0
2130456	Uh-22	0.02	0.27	0.34	0.37	0
2130476	Uhr-102	0.13	0.52	0.25	0.10	0
2130472	Uhr-49	0.15	0.49	0.25	0.11	0
2130473	Uhr-57	0.12	0.55	0.24	0.09	0
2130474	Uhr-64	0.12	0.56	0.23	0.09	0
2130475	Uhr-86	0.13	0.52	0.25	0.10	0
2130453	Zda-15	0.13	0.51	0.26	0.10	0

Tab. 4-13: n-alkanes and isoprenoid ratios of oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Sample lab No.	Well-No.	Pr/ Phy	Pr/n-C17	Phy/n-C18	n-C17/ (n-C17+27)
2140686	ZA-4a	1,383	2,246	1,099	0,761
2220144	ZA-4a	1,184	2,094	0,983	0,744
2130406	ZA-4a	2,015	0,824	0,493	0,705
2220147	ZA-8AH	1,355	2,151	0,873	0,794
2130467	Bor-1	1,588	0,564	0,410	0,750
2130468	Bor-2	2,074	0,518	0,370	0,753
2130469	Bor-3	1,424	0,554	0,448	0,751
2130470	Bor-4	2,002	0,557	0,313	0,771
2130457	Bos103	1,859	0,494	0,290	0,707
2130471	Boš-103	2,232	0,479	0,311	0,793
2130447	Kob-101	1,485	0,514	0,375	0,747
2130448	Kru-2	2,570	0,671	0,287	0,630
2130449	Nik-2A	1,411	26,483	22,601	0,649
2130451	Uh-102	1,420	0,491	0,307	0,666
2130476	Uh-102	1,734	0,494	0,306	0,638
2130452	Uh-16	1,620	0,376	0,232	0,531
2130454	Uh-19	1,281	0,558	0,783	0,824
2130455	Uh-2	2,295	0,482	0,245	0,783
2130456	Uh-22	1,727	0,367	0,198	0,717
2130472	Uh-49	1,758	0,522	0,317	0,710
2130473	Uh-57	1,800	0,533	0,408	0,954
2130474	Uh-64	2,233	0,681	0,425	0,943
2130475	Uh-86	2,379	0,643	0,232	0,707
2140690	Zd-146	1,316	5,903	3,932	0,791
2130453	Zd-15	1,516	0,512	0,386	0,735
2140691	Zd-173	0,668	6,194	3,271	0,473
2140689	Zd-52	1,827	1,317	0,952	0,642

Tab. 4-14: n-alkanes and isoprenoid ratios of oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Sample lab No.	Well-No.	% Norpr	%Pr	%Ph	CPI-2	n-C31/ n-C19
2140686	ZA-4a	39,174	35,302	25,524	2,299	0,371
2220144	ZA-4a	40,131	32,451	27,418	1,598	0,326
2130406	ZA-4a	24,555	50,425	25,020	1,140	0,163
2220147	ZA-8AH	39,519	34,794	25,686	2,405	0,434
2130467	Bor-1	33,101	41,047	25,852	1,043	0,193
2130468	Bor-2	33,092	45,145	21,763	1,004	0,256
2130469	Bor-3	32,586	39,602	27,811	1,101	0,190
2130470	Bor-4	37,080	41,962	20,957	1,082	0,218
2130457	Bos103	36,035	41,592	22,372	0,955	0,175
2130471	Boš-103	35,497	44,547	19,956	1,113	0,174
2130447	Kob-101	35,226	38,709	26,064	1,067	0,115
2130448	Kru-2	31,236	49,501	19,263	1,166	0,275
2130449	Nik-2A	35,495	37,752	26,752	1,413	0,415
2130451	Uh-102	35,043	38,113	26,844	1,048	0,172
2130476	Uh-102	36,787	40,090	23,123	1,063	0,290
2130452	Uh-16	34,631	40,415	24,954	1,058	0,313
2130454	Uh-19	61,835	21,434	16,731	6,408	0,501
2130455	Uh-2	30,607	48,332	21,060	1,056	0,164
2130456	Uh-22	28,117	45,520	26,364	0,963	0,176
2130472	Uh-49	36,001	40,797	23,203	1,074	0,206
2130473	Uh-57	42,074	37,238	20,687	1,054	0,018
2130474	Uh-64	38,066	42,777	19,156	1,080	0,030
2130475	Uh-86	31,942	47,916	20,142	1,009	0,244
2140690	Zd-146	31,587	38,869	29,543	0,797	0,966
2130453	Zd-15	36,115	38,489	25,396	1,078	0,117
2140691	Zd-173	27,782	28,934	43,284	0,713	0,368
2140689	Zd-52	32,390	43,692	23,918	1,031	0,596

Tab. 4-15: Facies related ratios of oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields based on biomarkers

Sample lab No.	Well No.	TERPANES				
		C35H C31..C35H	C35H C29..C33H	%28t	%29t	%30t
2140686	ZA-4a	0,030	0,11	6,8	35,2	58,1
2130406	ZA-4a	0,022	0,24	6,9	24,9	68,1
2220144	ZA-4a	0,031	0,11	6,2	33,1	60,7
2220147	ZA-8AH	0,031	0,11	6,2	39,7	54,1
2130467	Bor-1	0,021	0,17	11,9	39,8	48,3
2130468	Bor-2	0,023	0,16	9,2	40,5	50,3
2130469	Bor-3	0,025	0,20	8,8	36,6	54,6
2130470	Bor-4	0,022	0,15	8,6	38,0	53,4
2130457	Bos103	0,019	0,19	9,6	35,9	54,4
2130471	Bos-103	0,024	0,23	7,5	41,4	51,1
2130447	Kob-101	0,021	0,33	11,9	38,6	49,5
2130448	Kru-2	0,020	0,14	9,6	32,4	58,0
2130449	Nik-2A	0,021	0,26	11,8	38,8	49,3
2130451	Uh-102	0,020	0,26	12,3	37,1	50,6
2130476	Uh-102	0,022	0,18	9,1	38,5	52,3
2130452	Uh-16	0,016	0,25	12,9	36,0	51,1
2130454	Uh-19	0,022	0,20	15,3	32,9	51,8
2130455	Uh-2	0,020	0,25	8,5	37,1	54,4
2130456	Uh-22	0,013	0,40	9,2	36,4	54,4
2130472	Uh-49	0,020	0,18	8,4	37,8	53,8
2130473	Uh-57	0,026	0,21	7,9	38,5	53,6
2130474	Uh-64	0,023	0,17	7,7	44,5	47,8
2130475	Uh-86	0,023	0,17	9,3	35,6	55,1
2140690	Zd-146	0,041	0,09	7,7	40,4	51,9
2130453	Zd-15	0,037	0,14	14,8	35,0	50,2
2140691	Zd-173	0,043	0,08	8,6	39,2	52,2
2140689	Zd-52	0,051	0,07	7,9	43,5	48,5

Tab. 4-16: Facies related ratios of oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields based on biomarkers

Sample lab No.	Well No.	TERPANES					
		Tri-cyclic/ 30Hop 23t/ 30H	Tri-cyclic/ 30Hop 28t+29t/ 30H	Tetra- cyclic Index	Ext. Tri Index	ETR C28+29t (S+R) /Ts	Gmc indx30 10*Gmc/ (H+Gmc)
2140686	ZA-4a	0,54	0,11	3,40	0,27	0,276	0,39
2130406	ZA-4a	1,36	0,14	3,07	0,45	0,277	0,22
2220144	ZA-4a	0,53	0,11	3,64	0,28	0,259	0,41
2220147	ZA-8AH	0,49	0,11	3,69	0,24	0,279	0,41
2130467	Bor-1	0,74	0,17	3,31	0,33	0,335	0,37
2130468	Bor-2	0,70	0,16	3,36	0,32	0,311	0,32
2130469	Bor-3	0,75	0,15	1,43	0,34	0,257	0,31
2130470	Bor-4	0,67	0,14	3,56	0,30	0,313	0,32
2130457	Bos103	0,87	0,15	3,62	0,34	0,286	0,28
2130471	Bos-103	0,87	0,21	1,31	0,43	0,339	0,35
2130447	Kob-101	1,59	0,20	3,31	0,40	0,326	0,24
2130448	Kru-2	0,59	0,12	3,48	0,29	0,300	0,25
2130449	Nik-2A	1,08	0,15	3,91	0,30	0,294	0,25
2130451	Uh-102	1,15	0,18	3,74	0,37	0,309	0,27
2130476	Uh-102	0,80	0,15	3,44	0,31	0,292	0,32
2130452	Uh-16	1,01	0,21	2,70	0,42	0,322	0,54
2130454	Uh-19	0,90	0,19	3,80	0,40	0,312	0,37
2130455	Uh-2	0,95	0,16	1,49	0,36	0,243	0,28
2130456	Uh-22	1,40	0,23	2,42	0,50	0,284	0,26
2130472	Uh-49	0,77	0,15	3,31	0,32	0,296	0,32
2130473	Uh-57	1,13	0,17	3,30	0,38	0,304	0,33
2130474	Uh-64	0,82	0,20	3,82	0,38	0,333	0,37
2130475	Uh-86	0,82	0,13	2,89	0,29	0,233	0,28
2140690	Zd-146	0,41	0,10	3,39	0,21	0,295	0,32
2130453	Zd-15	0,82	0,12	2,29	0,24	0,329	0,17
2140691	Zd-173	0,40	0,09	3,19	0,19	0,280	0,29
2140689	Zd-52	0,36	0,10	3,42	0,19	0,311	0,29

Tab. 4-17: Facies related ratios of oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields based on biomarkers

Sample lab No.	Well No.	TERPANES					
		Sterane Index Ster/Hop	C29*Ts C29H	C29H/ C30H	Ts Tm	BNH BNH+C30t	C30dH C30H
2140686	ZA-4a	0,47	0,619	0,43	1,178	0,02	0,032
2130406	ZA-4a	0,59	0,590	0,48	1,110	0,13	0,041
2220144	ZA-4a	0,49	0,603	0,46	1,184	0,02	0,023
2220147	ZA-8AH	0,49	0,599	0,43	1,177	0,03	0,029
2130467	Bor-1	0,57	0,580	0,47	0,864	0,04	0,039
2130468	Bor-2	0,59	0,645	0,45	1,237	0,06	0,033
2130469	Bor-3	0,58	0,571	0,48	1,466	0,07	0,037
2130470	Bor-4	0,56	0,605	0,46	1,104	0,06	0,029
2130457	Bos103	0,58	0,598	0,65	1,155	0,11	0,026
2130471	Bos-103	0,58	0,653	0,46	1,251	0,04	0,046
2130447	Kob-101	0,63	0,619	0,50	1,140	0,06	0,025
2130448	Kru-2	0,55	0,488	0,51	0,868	0,08	0,036
2130449	Nik-2A	0,62	0,511	0,50	1,246	0,07	0,023
2130451	Uh-102	0,63	0,610	0,49	1,101	0,04	0,023
2130476	Uh-102	0,56	0,635	0,46	1,185	0,05	0,028
2130452	Uh-16	0,65	0,660	0,48	1,235	0,41	0,073
2130454	Uh-19	0,60	0,696	0,47	0,962	0,08	0,038
2130455	Uh-2	0,61	0,635	0,47	1,286	0,05	0,029
2130456	Uh-22	0,70	0,753	0,49	1,491	0,09	0,032
2130472	Uh-49	0,57	0,610	0,47	1,126	0,04	0,029
2130473	Uh-57	0,56	0,722	0,45	1,254	0,02	0,065
2130474	Uh-64	0,55	0,743	0,42	1,333	0,04	0,038
2130475	Uh-86	0,57	0,602	0,46	1,498	0,04	0,035
2140690	Zd-146	0,46	0,522	0,44	1,127	0,01	0,022
2130453	Zd-15	0,52	0,438	0,45	1,063	0,06	0,007
2140691	Zd-173	0,45	0,502	0,42	1,157	0,03	0,022
2140689	Zd-52	0,41	0,476	0,43	1,128	0,02	0,015

Tab. 4-18: Facies related ratios of oils from Zar-3 and adjacent fields based on biomarkers

Sample lab No.	Well No.	STERANES					THIOPHENES
		C27 %abb	C28 %abb m/z 218	C29 %abb	C29/27 abb m/z 218	C28/29 abb m/z 218	DBT/ (P+DBT)
2140686	ZA-4a	41,71	23,36	34,93	0,84	0,67	0,08
2130406	ZA-4a	40,73	23,19	36,08	0,89	0,64	0,08
2220144	ZA-4a	39,15	24,64	36,21	0,93	0,68	0,08
2220147	ZA-8AH	40,25	24,56	35,19	0,87	0,70	0,08
2130467	Bor-1	41,42	26,48	32,10	0,78	0,82	0,09
2130468	Bor-2	42,75	25,99	31,26	0,73	0,83	0,08
2130469	Bor-3	42,22	26,29	31,49	0,75	0,83	0,10
2130470	Bor-4	41,10	26,25	32,65	0,79	0,80	0,08
2130457	Bos103	43,44	24,92	31,64	0,73	0,79	0,07
2130471	Bos-103	43,65	25,31	31,03	0,71	0,82	0,10
2130447	Kob-101	46,78	24,18	29,04	0,62	0,83	0,07
2130448	Kru-2	41,33	25,81	32,86	0,79	0,79	0,09
2130449	Nik-2A	45,24	23,26	31,49	0,70	0,74	0,14
2130451	Uh-102	45,66	24,66	29,68	0,65	0,83	0,08
2130476	Uh-102	41,07	26,39	32,54	0,79	0,81	0,08
2130452	Uh-16	40,51	30,81	28,68	0,71	1,07	0,20
2130454	Uh-19	42,14	27,30	30,56	0,73	0,89	0,20
2130455	Uh-2	45,74	24,40	29,87	0,65	0,82	0,12
2130456	Uh-22	49,16	23,50	27,34	0,56	0,86	0,18
2130472	Uh-49	40,74	26,54	32,71	0,80	0,81	0,08
2130473	Uh-57	44,02	25,34	30,64	0,70	0,83	0,07
2130474	Uh-64	42,35	27,67	29,98	0,71	0,92	0,08
2130475	Uh-86	39,75	25,22	35,03	0,88	0,72	0,08
2140690	Zd-146	39,19	25,24	35,57	0,91	0,71	0,22
2130453	Zd-15	39,99	27,17	32,84	0,82	0,83	0,08
2140691	Zd-173	38,24	26,49	35,27	0,92	0,75	0,25
2140689	Zd-52	39,09	25,94	34,96	0,89	0,74	0,12

Tab. 4-19: Thermal maturity of oils based on biomarker - samples from Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Sample lab No.	Well No.	TERPANES					
		$\frac{C31H}{22S} \frac{22S}{22S+22R}$	$\frac{C32H}{22S} \frac{22S}{22S+22R}$	$\frac{C30M}{C30H+C30M}$	$\frac{3R}{3R+5R}$	$\frac{T_s}{T_s+T_m}$	$\frac{29*T_s}{NH+29*T_s}$
2140686	ZA-4a	0,557	0,577	0,118	0,086	0,541	0,383
2130406	ZA-4a	0,579	0,571	0,115	0,166	0,526	0,371
2220144	ZA-4a	0,567	0,563	0,147	0,087	0,542	0,376
2220147	ZA-8AH	0,566	0,561	0,120	0,084	0,541	0,374
2130467	Bor-1	0,568	0,567	0,112	0,118	0,464	0,367
2130468	Bor-2	0,570	0,572	0,105	0,116	0,553	0,392
2130469	Bor-3	0,571	0,520	0,121	0,132	0,594	0,363
2130457	Bos-103	0,573	0,587	0,114	0,137	0,536	0,374
2130471	Bos-103	0,575	0,582	0,104	0,146	0,556	0,395
2130470	Boš-4	0,569	0,515	0,116	0,112	0,525	0,377
2130447	Kob-101	0,575	0,581	0,112	0,219	0,533	0,382
2130448	Kru-2	0,560	0,555	0,141	0,104	0,465	0,328
2130449	Nik-2A	0,567	0,564	0,105	0,180	0,555	0,338
2130451	Uh-102	0,575	0,576	0,110	0,176	0,524	0,379
2130452	Uh-16	0,577	0,583	0,112	0,155	0,553	0,397
2130454	Uh-19	0,576	0,574	0,113	0,140	0,490	0,410
2130455	Uh-2	0,570	0,585	0,109	0,164	0,563	0,389
2130456	Uh-22	0,569	0,511	0,105	0,252	0,599	0,430
2130476	Uhř-102	0,575	0,569	0,109	0,131	0,542	0,389
2130472	Uhř-49	0,577	0,579	0,113	0,132	0,530	0,379
2130473	Uhř-57	0,574	0,571	0,105	0,150	0,556	0,419
2130474	Uhř-64	0,567	0,579	0,106	0,123	0,571	0,426
2130475	Uhř-86	0,574	0,575	0,105	0,123	0,600	0,376
2140690	ZD-146	0,559	0,567	0,122	0,067	0,530	0,343
2130453	ZD-15	0,572	0,572	0,118	0,099	0,515	0,305
2140691	ZD-173	0,560	0,558	0,127	0,063	0,536	0,334
2140689	ZD-52	0,561	0,569	0,121	0,056	0,530	0,322

Tab. 4-20: Thermal maturity of oils based on biomarker - samples from Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Sample lab No.	Well No.	STERANES				MDBT
		C29 _20S 20S+20R	C27 _20S 20S+20R	29,00 _abb aaa+abb	27,00 _ba aaa+ba	MDR 4MDT/ (4+1MDT)
2140686	ZA-4a	0,453	0,652	0,589	0,695	0,838
2130406	ZA-4a	0,570	0,344	0,599	0,821	0,842
2220144	ZA-4a	0,460	0,635	0,575	0,682	0,661
2220147	ZA-8AH	0,481	0,614	0,570	0,682	0,661
2130467	Bor-1	0,461	0,562	0,542	0,718	0,719
2130468	Bor-2	0,495	0,558	0,543	0,733	0,783
2130469	Bor-3	0,476	0,573	0,549	0,712	0,720
2130457	Bos-103	0,435	0,305	0,536	0,818	0,818
2130471	Bos-103	0,586	0,645	0,698	0,844	0,770
2130470	Boš-4	0,485	0,551	0,551	0,706	0,790
2130447	Kob-101	0,531	0,228	0,551	0,838	0,755
2130448	Kru-2	0,395	0,243	0,496	0,777	0,735
2130449	Nik-2A	0,392	0,145	0,482	0,726	0,797
2130451	Uh-102	0,501	0,257	0,568	0,816	0,806
2130452	Uh-16	0,523	0,304	0,571	0,797	0,930
2130454	Uh-19	0,630	0,538	0,714	0,880	0,581
2130455	Uh-2	0,490	0,282	0,575	0,827	0,792
2130456	Uh-22	0,563	0,321	0,596	0,821	0,914
2130476	Uhř-102	0,478	0,575	0,567	0,713	0,806
2130472	Uhř-49	0,504	0,552	0,556	0,716	0,816
2130473	Uhř-57	0,518	0,568	0,585	0,779	0,797
2130474	Uhř-64	0,533	0,546	0,578	0,766	0,794
2130475	Uhř-86	0,484	0,593	0,603	0,718	0,807
2140690	ZD-146	0,383	0,595	0,494	0,588	0,375
2130453	ZD-15	0,365	0,186	0,434	0,720	0,731
2140691	ZD-173	0,379	0,549	0,497	0,578	0,028
2140689	ZD-52	0,360	0,566	0,501	0,609	0,740

Tab. 4-21: Thermal maturity of oils based on biomarker - samples from Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Sample lab No.	Well No.	PHEN		
		MPI-1 -	MPDF -	Rc(MPI1) [0.5-1.4] (%)
2140686	ZA-4a	0,785	0,541	0,859
2130406	ZA-4a	0,766	0,526	0,847
2220144	ZA-4a	0,783	0,529	0,858
2220147	ZA-8AH	0,778	0,529	0,855
2130467	Bor-1	0,715	0,464	0,816
2130468	Bor-2	0,656	0,451	0,780
2130469	Bor-3	0,701	0,468	0,808
2130457	Bos-103	0,741	0,510	0,832
2130471	Bos-103	0,624	0,463	0,760
2130470	Boš-4	0,669	0,469	0,788
2130447	Kob-101	0,748	0,507	0,836
2130448	Kru-2	0,632	0,461	0,766
2130449	Nik-2A	1,019	0,534	1,002
2130451	Uh-102	0,725	0,501	0,822
2130452	Uh-16	1,060	0,630	1,027
2130454	Uh-19	0,358	0,308	0,599
2130455	Uh-2	0,705	0,477	0,810
2130456	Uh-22	1,017	0,634	1,000
2130476	Uhř-102	0,728	0,502	0,824
2130472	Uhř-49	0,742	0,506	0,833
2130473	Uhř-57	0,693	0,476	0,803
2130474	Uhř-64	0,700	0,481	0,807
2130475	Uhř-86	0,725	0,502	0,822
2140690	ZD-146	0,642	0,366	0,772
2130453	ZD-15	0,547	0,423	0,713
2140691	ZD-173	1,077	0,467	1,037
2140689	ZD-52	0,718	0,468	0,818

4.2 Gas Composition

Chemical composition of the produced gas from the Žarošice field is in Tabs. 4-22 to 4-30.

Tab. 4-22: Archival data of chemical composition of gas samples from Zar-3 field (MND)

No.	Unit	1	2	3	4	5	6
Za-well #		ZA3	ZA3	ZA4A	ZA4A	ZA4A	ZA5H
Depth 1	m	1740	1740	1802	1802	1802	2550
Depth 2	m	1780	1780	1842	1842	1842	2860
MND No.		147\2002	436\2002	2024\2002	1562\2003	3232\2018	978\2010
Sampling date		16.1.2002	7.2.2002	11.6.2002	15.5.2003	5.6.2018	5.3.2010
Sampling details		through separator	through separator	through separator	through separator	from annulus	through separator
Methane	% mol.	83.31	83.372	84.291	84.458	90.615	84.094
Ethane	% mol.	7.60	7.59	7.059	6.988	3.566	5.950
Propane	% mol.	0.93	0.88	0.60	0.94	0.282	0.595
2-MP	% mol.	0.33	0.33	0.21	0.29	0.088	0.145
n-Butane	% mol.	0.30	0.30	0.18	0.23	0.054	0.108
2-Metylbutane	% mol.	0.10	0.10	0.06	0.09	0.021	0.040
n-Pentane	% mol.	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.06	0.012	0.028
Hexanes	% mol.	0.17	0.19	0.17	0.15	0.062	0.060
Oxygen	% mol.	<0.001	<0.005	<0.005	<0.005	<0.005	<0.005
Nitrogen	% mol.	0.08	0.08	0.12	0.09	0.150	0.083
Carbon dioxide	% mol.	7.13	7.09	7.26	6.71	5.143	8.898
Helium	% mol.	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	<0.001
Hydrogen sulphide	mg/m3	<2	<2	1,40	2,00	584	-

Tab. 4-23: Archival data of chemical composition of gas samples from Zar-3 field (MND)

No.	Unit	7	8	9	10	11
Za-well #		ZA6a	ZA8AH	ZA8AH	ZA9AH	ZA14H
Depth 1	m	1899	2338	2338	2202	2117
Depth 2	m	2000	2440	2440	2475	2255
MND No.		2896\2003	2668\2015	2669\2015	4419\2004	3233\2018
Sampling date		26.8.2003	28.4.2015	28.4.2015	27.12.2004	5.6.2018
Sampling details		at well head	from tubing at well head	from annulus at well head	through separator	at well head
Methane	% mol.	82.013	91.573	92.070	86.349	89.087
Ethane	% mol.	6.617	4.072	3.861	5.254	3.568
Propane	% mol.	0.45	0.445	0.482	0.266	0.192
2-MP	% mol.	0.16	0.130	0.145	0.081	0.077
n-Butane	% mol.	0.15	0.102	0.129	0.044	0.053
2-Metylbutane	% mol.	0.04	0.037	0.054	0.019	0.019
n-Pentane	% mol.	0.04	0.025	0.041	0.010	0.016
Hexanes	% mol.	0.11	0.083	0.096	0.044	0.094
Oxygen	% mol.	<0.005	0.008	0.005	<0.005	<0.005
Nitrogen	% mol.	0.05	0.345	0.375	0.105	0.097
Carbon dioxide	% mol.	10.37	3.174	2.736	7.826	6.792
Helium	% mol.	0.001	0.006	0.006	<0.001	0.001
Hydrogen sulphide	mg/m ³	<2	11	<2	<2	8

Tab. 4-24: Chemical composition of gas samples from the Zar-3 field (CGS)

No.		12	13	14	15	16	17
Well	No.	ZA4a	ZA4a	ZA4a	Zar8AH	ZA14H	ZA14H
Sampling	date	05.11.21	05.11.21	02.12.21	17.05.22	05.11.21	05.11.21
Sample	lab No.	2130489	2130490	2140685	2220146	2130491	2130492
He	(%)	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	0.0064	< 0.01	< 0.01
H ₂	(%)	< 0.007	0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007
CO ₂	(%)	4.878	0.643	21.550	1.395	5.750	5.837
Ar	(%)	< 0.03	0.22	0.15	0.08	< 0.03	< 0.03
O ₂	(%)	< 0.2	1.12	2.72	< 0.2	< 0.2	< 0.2
N ₂	(%)	0.7585	6.3550	9.4993	3.7726	1.2828	0.8272
Metane	(%)	89.4761	86.3542	50.555	89.919	89.274	89.314
CO	(%)	0.1061	0.0784	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05
Etene	(%)	< 0.0001	0.0004	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Etane	(%)	4.3660	4.7579	11.5192	3.8645	3.3847	3.6808
Propene	(%)	< 0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Propane	(%)	0.2411	0.2688	1.7014	0.5063	0.1695	0.1858
Isobutene	(%)	0.0802	0.0894	0.8885	0.1541	0.0550	0.0603
n-butane	(%)	0.0461	0.0513	0.6197	0.1267	0.0419	0.0463
2,2-DMpropane	(%)	0.0015	0.0018	0.0216	0.0024	0.0014	0.0017
2-Mbutane	(%)	0.0176	0.0201	0.3055	0.0502	0.0139	0.0153
n-pentane	(%)	0.0103	0.0112	0.1851	0.0366	0.0113	0.0127
Cyklopentane	(%)	0.0010	0.0010	0.0223	0.0029	0.0013	0.0015
sum i-C ₆ -1	(%)	0.0083	0.0198	0.1533	0.0549	0.0088	0.0101
n-hexane	(%)	0.0025	0.0031	0.0651	0.0129	0.0036	0.0042

Tab. 4-25: Isotopic composition of gas samples from the Zar-3 field (CGS)

No.		12	13	14	15	16	17
Well	No.	ZA4a	ZA4a	ZA4a	Zar8AH	ZA14H	ZA14H
Sampling	date	05.11.21	05.11.21	02.12.21	17.05.22	05.11.21	05.11.21
Sample	lab No.	2130489	2130490	2140685	2220146	2130491	2130492
d ¹³ C-CO ₂	(‰)	9.3	8.5	16.2	6.9	11.2	10.4
sd d ¹³ C-CO ₂	(‰)	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1
d ¹³ C-C1	(‰)	-37.3	-38.2	-37.2	-37.9	-39	-38.6
d ¹³ C-C2	(‰)	-23.7	-23.8	-23.8	-23.6	-23.8	-23.9
d13-C3	(‰)	-19.0	-19.2	-19.6	-21.1	-19.6	-19.4
d13-iC4	(‰)				-25.1		
d13-nC4	(‰)				-22.6		
dD-C1	(‰)				-179.0		
Dd ¹³ C-(CO ₂ -C1)	(‰)	46.6	46.7	53.4	44.7	50.2	49.0
Dd ¹³ C-(C2-C1)	(‰)	13.6	14.4	13.4	14.3	15.2	14.7
Dd ¹³ C-(C3-C2)	(‰)	4.7	4.6	4.2	2.5	4.2	4.5
C1/(C2+3)		19.42	17.18	3.82	20.57	25.12	23.10
C1/C2		20.5	18.1	4.4	23.3	26.4	24.3
C2/C3		18.1	17.7	6.8	7.6	20.0	19.8
C1/(C1+CO ₂)		0.95	0.99	0.70	0.98	0.94	0.94
CO ₂ /(C1+CO ₂)		0.05	0.01	0.30	0.02	0.06	0.06

Tab. 4-26: Chemical and isotopic composition of soil gas samples from the Zar-3 field, collected at depth 0,1-0,8 m (CGS)

Lab No.	2130483	2130484	2130485	2130486	2130487	2130488
Probe No.	14	21	23	41	50	67
Sampling date	05.11.21	05.11.21	05.11.21	05.11.21	05.11.21	05.11.21
He (%)	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
H ₂ (%)	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007
CO ₂ (%)	0.247	2.551	0.937	0.661	6.130	7.188
Ar (%)	0.85	0.85	0.84	0.78	0.93	0.30
O ₂ (%)	22.49	20.78	22.59	23.87	14.71	9.14
N ₂ (%)	76.41	75.81	75.63	74.69	78.23	83.37
Metane (%)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
CO (%)	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05
Ehtene (%)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Ethane (%)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Propene (%)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Propane (%)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Isobutane (%)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
n-Butane (%)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
2,2-Dmpropane (%)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
2-Mbutane (%)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.0007	0.0002	0.0006	0.0002
n-pentane (%)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Cyklopentane (%)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
sum i-C ₆ -1 (%)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
n-Hexan (%)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)	-17.8	-20.2	-19.1	-19.3	-20.4	-20.2
sd δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.0

Tab. 4-27: Chemical and isotopic composition of soil gas samples from the Zar-3 field, collected at depth 0,1-0,8 m (CGS)

Lab No.		2140688	2310151	2310152	2310153	2310154
Probe No.			102	29	120	123
Sampling date		02.12.21	27.01.23	27.01.23	27.01.23	27.01.23
He (‰)		< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
H ₂ (‰)		< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007
CO ₂ (‰)		1.102	0.831	1.255	0.177	2.399
Ar (‰)		0.84	0.936	0.968	0.912	0.940
O ₂ (‰)		19.64	20.89	18.87	23.42	20.02
N ₂ (‰)		78.41	77.34	78.91	75.49	76.64
Metane (‰)		< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
CO (‰)		< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05
Ehtene (‰)		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Ethane (‰)		< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Propene (‰)		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Propane (‰)		< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Isobutane (‰)		< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
n-Butane (‰)		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
2,2-Dmpropane (‰)		< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
2-Mbutane (‰)		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
n-pentane (‰)		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Cyklopentane (‰)		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
sum i-C ₆ -1 (‰)		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
n-Hexan (‰)		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)		-19.8	-22.4	-21.7	-19.7	-21.7
sd δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)		0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1

Tab. 4-28: Chemical and isotopic composition of soil gas samples from the Zar-3 field, collected at depth 0,1-0,8 m (CGS)

Lab No.	2310155	2310195	2310196	2320266	2320267
Probe No.	109	120	JP7	111	123
Sampling date	27.01.23	16.2.23	16.2.23	01.06.23	01.06.23
He (‰)	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	0	0
H ₂ (‰)	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	0	0
CO ₂ (‰)	0.585	0.563	0.065	2.681	4.024
Ar (‰)	0.925	0.922	0.923	0.969	0.979
O ₂ (‰)	22.75	20.26	20.89	13.87	12.56
N ₂ (‰)	75.74	78.26	77.91	82.48	82.44
Metane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	0.2106	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
CO (‰)	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05
Ehtene (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Ethane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Propene (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Propane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Isobutane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
n-Butane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
2,2-Dmpropane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
2-Mbutane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
n-pentane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Cyklopentane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
sum i-C ₆ -1 (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
n-Hexan (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)	-21.0			-15.4	-15.6
sd δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)	0.2			0.1	0.1

Tab. 4-29: Chemical and isotopic composition of soil gas samples from the Zar-3 field, collected at depth 0,1-0,8 m (CGS)

Lab No.	2320272	2320273	2330361	2340368	2340369
Probe No.	29	62	106	7	46
Sampling date	01.06.23	01.06.23	24.08.23	02.10.23	02.10.23
He (‰)	0	0	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
H ₂ (‰)	0	0	< 0.007	< 0.007	0.008
CO ₂ (‰)	2.002	2.371	1.900	4.003	2.363
Ar (‰)	0.934	0.925	0.940	0.948	0.926
O ₂ (‰)	17.94	17.16	18.90	17.65	19.78
N ₂ (‰)	79.12	79.55	78.23	77.40	76.92
Metane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
CO (‰)	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05
Ehtene (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Ethane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Propene (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Propane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Isobutane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
n-Butane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
2,2-Dmpropane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
2-Mbutane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
n-pentane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Cyklopentane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
sum i-C ₆ -1 (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
n-Hexan (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.0001	< 0.0001
δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)	-16.6	-14.5	-18.5	-19.5	-19.4
sd δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)	0.3	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1

Tab. 4-30: Chemical and isotopic composition of soil gas samples from the Zar-3 field, collected at depth 0,1-0,8 m (CGS)

Lab No.	2340370	2340371	2340372	2340373	2340374
Probe No.	67	119	123	124	127
Sampling date	03.10.23	04.10.23	04.10.23	04.10.23	04.10.23
He (‰)	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
H ₂ (‰)	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007	< 0.007
CO ₂ (‰)	2.867	0.146	3.361	2.819	3.482
Ar (‰)	0.931	0.888	0.961	0.941	0.992
O ₂ (‰)	19.99	25.12	15.13	17.84	14.29
N ₂ (‰)	76.21	73.85	80.55	78.40	81.23
Metane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
CO (‰)	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05
Ehtene (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Ethane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Propene (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Propane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
Isobutane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
n-Butane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
2,2-Dmpropane (‰)	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002	< 0.0002
2-Mbutane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
n-pentane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Cyklopentane (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
sum i-C ₆ -1 (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
n-Hexan (‰)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)	-19.7	-18.5	-21.1	-21.4	-21.8
sd δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ (‰)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1

4.3 Formation water composition

Chemical composition of the produced formation water samples from the Žarošice field is in Tab. 4-31. Review of formation water from Zar-3 and adjacent oil & gas fields reservoirs and caprocks are in Tab. 4-32.

Tab. 4-31: Archival data on chemical composition of formation water from the Zar-3 field

No.	Unit	1	2	3	4
Za-well#		ZA4A	ZA5H	ZA8AH	ZA8AH
Depth 1	m	1802,3	2550,2	2338,0	2338,0
Depth 2	m	2842	2860	2440	2440
MND laboratory number		1524\2012	6680\2015	2301\2015	3029\2016
Sampling date		21.3.2012	9.9.2015	10.4.2015	2.6.2016
Density at 15°C	g/cm ³		1.0177	1.0178	
pH		7.09	7.25	8.43	7.25
El. conductivity at 25°C	mS/cm	36.0	36.0	37.5	38.3
Amonium ion NH ₄	mg/l	<1.30	31.4	13.0	32.4
Chlorides Cl	mg/l	12000	12700	12200	11700
Bicarbonates HCO ₃	mg/l	2800	2480	2150	1880
Iodine I	mg/l	68	51	68	68
Bromine Br	mg/l	77	71	83	230
KNK-4,5	mmol/l		40.7		30.8
Sulphates SO ₄	mg/l	866	1130		1410
Magnesium Mg	mg/l	96.0	137	135	133
Calcium Ca	mg/l	401	116	22.5	440
total hardness	mmol/l	27.9	8.53	6.11	16.5
Total dissolved solids TDS	mg/l	25170	26130	24230	24450
Barium Ba	mg/l	1.04	<2.50	<0.50	<2.50
Iron Fe	mg/l	16.9	1.34	18.8	14.9
Manganese Mn	mg/l				0.420
Lithium Li	mg/l	2.90	3.36	3.17	3.29
Rubidium Rb	mg/l	0.28	0.35		0.52
Stroncium Sr	mg/l	26.2	23.0	6.23	26.1
Sodium Na	mg/l	8200	8890	8710	8070
Potassium K	mg/l	411	271	482	473
Sulphide sulphur (S ²⁻)	mg/l				<0.2
Silicic acid H ₂ SiO ₃	mg/l	11.6	42.3	32.5	31.5
Boric acid HBO ₂	mg/l	197	179	305	231

Tab. 4-32: Archival data on chemical composition of formation waters from the Zar-3 and adjacent oil & gas fields: overburden caprocks, reservoirs and underburden Paleozoics and fractured crystalline basement (Fig. 15-19)

Ždánice-Hustopeče + Menilite Fms.		Němčice Fm.		Nesvačilka Fm.		Vranovice + Mikulov Fms.	
Depth (m)	TDS (mg/L)	Depth (m)	TDS (mg/L)	Depth (m)	TDS (mg/L)	Depth (m)	TDS (mg/L)
592	7 391	1 247	11 205	2 664	19 209	1640	17000,02
990	2 863	1 234	11 455	2 572	20 534	1912	25170
370	2 195	1 210	12 752	2 387	23 445	1812	26130
394	3 852	1 143	11 935	2 700	19 825	1801	24230
592	6 830	785	20 750	2 282	21 209	2105	14736,7
1 188	8 519	785	21 695	2 314	19 243	2075	20413,8
643	1 972	1 507	15 470	1 863	14 820	1952	23012,8
590	2 106	984	15 288	2 059	17 341	1940	23684,9
520	1 602	888	22 157	3 051	29 986	1521,5	21839,1
394	3 649			3 134	32 135	2885	22061,66
870	3 740			3 054	32 395	2742	22816,96
795	6 577					1848	24605,92
1 995	17 100					1812	24513,12
1 561	8 939						

Nikolčice+ Gresten Fms.		Devon. carbonates Myslejovice Fm.		Devonian clastics + crystalline basement	
Depth (m)	TDS (mg/L)	Depth (m)	TDS (mg/L)	Depth (m)	TDS (mg/L)
2 195	20 876	1 360	17 992	1 001	14 962
1 685	20 451	1 310	16 135	1 350	20 755
1 890	17 031	1 283	19 172	2 995	23 128
1 564	22 705	1 195	19 719	1 460	17 010
2 899	23 227	2 483	32 736	1 405	21 756
2 847	20 272	2 470	33 768	1 362	18 324
2 842	21 099	2 310	23 363	3 575	32 250
2 829	22 394	2 930	24 089		
2 928	22 466	2 815	28 235		
2 844	23 600	2 660	30 387		
2 683	21 369	2 030	20 005		
2 575	20 106	2 765	26 426		
2 600	20 091	2 350	19 919		
		3 050	23 330		
		3 025	22 852		

5 INTERPRETATIONS

5.1 Oils

The Zar-3 oil samples are classified as **medium sweet crude oils**. The whole oil analysis provided information on the gasoline and black oil fractions of oils (Fig. 5-1). The black oil is a residuum of the original oil accumulation affected by heavy biodegradation, which is classified as level 6 on the PM scale. The most striking feature (Fig. 2) is the UCM hump (unresolved compound mixture), which is a typical result of microbial biodegradation of oil at temperature below 65°C. No or almost no n-alkanes are preserved in the C₁₃-C₃₅ range. The original accumulation formed after oil generation from Jurassic source rocks after the emplacement of the West Carpathians on the Bohemian Massif in the Lower-Middle Miocene (16-16 Ma b.p.). The black oil is mixed with a gasoline range light hydrocarbons, which are only slightly biodegraded and are rich in n-alkanes, iso- and cyclo-alkanes. The light hydrocarbons show markedly higher thermal maturity and were generated from a greater burial depth than the black oil (Francu et al. 1996, Krejčí et al. 1994, 1996, Picha & Peters 1998). They migrated into the reservoirs during a later tectonic event, probably associated with transtensional movements in the West Carpathian fold-and-thrust belt in the Middle to Upper Miocene (13-9 Ma b.p.).

Fig. 5-1: ZA4a Whole-oil gas chromatogram with detailed distribution of light hydrocarbons in the C5-C13 range. Most biomarkers occur in the black oil molecular fraction.

Majority of hydrocarbons in the gasoline fraction are quantified and the derived transformation and correlation ratios are in Tab. 4-9 to 4-12. Transformation in

reservoir shows different steps of biodegradation of the gasoline range hydrocarbons from the first “victims” removed from the mixture (n-C7) to those more resistant “leftovers” (dimethylcyclopentane etc.). Additional alterations include water washing, which removes preferentially aromatic compounds, such as benzene, toluene and xylenes. Oils from Zar-3 and adjacent oil and gas fields are grouped based on the transformation ratios TR1 – TR8 (Figs. 5-2 to 5-6).

Fig. 5-2: Gasoline range hydrocarbons of all oils in the broader Zar-3 region.

Fig. 5-3: Transformation ratios (TR1-TR8) of the gasoline range hydrocarbons in the Ždánice oil field.

Fig. 5-4: Transformation ratios (TR1-TR8) of the gasoline range hydrocarbons in the second group of oils including Borkovany, Bošovice and Uhřice oil&gas fields.

3rd Group of oils

Fig. 5-5: Transformation ratios (TR1-TR8) of the gasoline range hydrocarbons in the third group of oils: Uhřice and Bošovice field.

Žarošice ZA4a + UH19

Fig. 5-6: Transformation ratios (TR1-TR8) of the gasoline range hydrocarbons in the Žarošice oil and gas field and Uhřice-19 (Mikulov Fm.). These oils show stronger biodegradation even of the light hydrocarbons than the rest of the studied oils.

5.2 Gas

The produced gas has relatively high content of carbon dioxide since field opening. The ZA8AH well samples represent different type of gas. H₂S started to occur in 2015, probably due to introduction of sulphate reducing bacteria (SRB) into the reservoir during storage of the produced and separated formation water from the produced suspension.

Fig. 5-7: Zar-3 gas characteristics are shown in “Bernard” type plot based on $\delta^{13}C (CH_4)$ carbon isotopic composition of methane and $C_1/(C_2+C_3)$ dryness index from ZA3, ZA4a, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA14H and reference gas samples from the Uhřice, Dambořice (Jurassic and Carboniferous reservoirs) and Klobouky, Bošovice, Hostěrádky, Násedlovice fields (Paleogene reservoirs). The outlines of the genetic types of thermogenic and microbial gas origin are adapted from Whiticar (1999).

Fig. 5-8: Genetic types of natural gas based on carbon and hydrogen isotopic composition of methane: ZA8H gas sample. Reference fields follow Whiticar et al (1986): MMF - microbial methyl type fermentation, MCR - microbial carbonate reduction, Thermal - thermogenic, Hy-thermal - hydrothermal geothermal (crystalline), Atm – atmospheric methane, Abio - abiogenic mantle methane.

Fig. 5-9: Zar-3 gas characteristics by $\delta^{13}\text{C}(\text{CH}_4)$ carbon isotopic composition of methane and $\delta^{13}\text{C}(\text{CO}_2)$ carbon dioxide.

Fig. 5-10: Zar-3 gas characteristics based on $\delta^{13}\text{C} (\text{CH}_4)$ carbon isotopic composition of methane in respect to depth from ZA3, ZA4a, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA14H and reference gas samples from the Uhřice, Dambořice (Jurassic and Carboniferous reservoirs) and Klobouky, Bošovice, Hostěrádky, Násedlovice fields (Paleogene reservoirs).

A few examples of microbial methane accumulations are added to Fig. 5-10 from Milešovice, Ždánice, Kroměříž and Nítkovice fields. The outlines of the genetic types of thermogenic and microbial gas origin are adapted from Whiticar (1999).

Fig. 5-11: Carbon dioxide content in gas (CO₂ %vol) in soil gas.

The soil gas samples contain CO₂ in the amount 0,146 - 7.188%vol, the carbon isotopic composition $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ ranges from -21.7 to -14.5‰.

5.2 Water

Formation water geochemical types from Zar-3 storage site and adjacent oil & gas fields are shown in Figs. 5-12 and 5-13.

Fig. 5-12: Piper plot of chemical composition of the formation water in the Žarošice and adjacent fields.

Fig. 5-13: Burov plot of chemical composition of formation water in the Žarošice and adjacent oil and gas fields.

Activity of SRB

Activity of sulfate reduction bacteria can be expressed by the following equation:

Hydrogen sulphide did not occur in the early produced oil and gas from tubing indications are that it did occur in the annulus. Human activity probably contributed to later occurrence of H₂S (e.g. during workover).

Formation water mineralization in reservoir and overburden rocks

Mineralization of pore water is controlled by the original depositional environment and secondary alterations due to fluid – rock interactions and infiltration of descending fresh water from the surface. Here the mineralization expressed as total dissolved solids (TDS) in water is shown in respect to true vertical depth (TVD sub sea) in the broader Zar-3 area of interest for the overburden caprocks, main reservoir and underlying formations.

Overburden includes

- overthrust Ždánice unit with Ždánice-Hustopeče, Menilite and Němčice Fms,
- autochthonous Paleogene – Nesvačilka Fm.

Reservoir

- Jurassic – Mikulov Fm. (mainly caprock with minor reservoir)
 - Vranovice Fm. (main reservoir – dolomite)
 - Nikolčice and Gresten Fms. (additional reservoir – dolomitic and quartz sandstone)

Underburden

- Carboniferous Myslejovice Fm. (sandstone/ shale turbidites)
- crystalline basement, Devonian carbonates.

Ždánice-Hustopeče and Menilite Fm.

Němčice (Submenilite) Fm.

Fig. 5-14: Mineralization of formation water in Ždánice-Hustopeče and Menilite Fms. and in Němčice Fm. in the Ždánice unit of the Carpathian Flysch Belt overthrust overlying the autochthonous units of the Bohemian Massif.

Fig. 5-15: Mineralization of formation water in the overburden Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm. acting as caprock in many oil & gas fields.

Vranovice and Mikulov Fm.

Nikolčice and Gresten Fm.

Fig. 5-16: Mineralization of formation water in the main reservoir – Jurassic Vranovice and Nikolčice Fms.

**Myslejovice Fm. (Kulm facies)
and Devonian Carbonates**

**Devonian clastics (Old Red facies) and
Crystalline basement - Precambrian**

Fig. 5-17: Mineralization of formation water in the turbidite type Myslejovice Fm., Devonian carbonates, siliciclastics and in the fractured crystalline basement below the Jurassic reservoirs.

Fig. 5-18: Mineralization of formation water in overburden, main reservoir and underburden strata of the broader region of Zar-3 storage site (summary of Figs 15-17).

Maximum fresh water infiltration into the overburden rocks is observed down to 1 km.

6. STATISTICAL EVALUATION

Statistical analysis of UPGMA type was calculated and the cluster diagram is in Fig. 6-1 showing grouping of the oils in the region based on similarity in light hydrocarbon distribution.

Fig. 6-1: Cluster analysis of similarity of gasoline range light hydrocarbon in the oils in Zar-3 and adjacent fields

Four to five genetic groups were identified among the gasoline fraction of the oils in the region. ZA4A oil is most similar to UH57, UH19 and NIK2A.

7. CONCLUSIONS

1. Oil in Zar-3 consists of gasoline range hydrocarbons and black oil, which are of different origin and migration phase.
2. Black oil fraction of the Zar-3 oil is heavily biodegraded in the reservoir. All n-alkanes are removed, UCM (unresolved hydrocarbon mixture) represents ca 78% of the oil. This feature is typical of higher biodegradation level (PM6). Thermal maturity of the black oil fraction is equivalent to vitrinite reflectance of 0,86%, which occurs in source rocks at depth of ca 5 km.
3. Light hydrocarbons (gasoline) is of considerably higher thermal maturity and migrated during a later phase of migration, probably in the Upper Miocene. Gasoline fraction is mildly biodegraded in the reservoir, n-alkanes are preserved.
4. Gasoline range hydrocarbons show a very high water washing effect evidenced by loss of aromatic hydrocarbons and more intensive biodegradation than the adjacent oil fields.
5. Four to five genetic groups were identified among the gasoline fraction of the oils in the region. ZA4A oil is most similar to UH57, UH19 and NIK2A.
6. Gas in Zar-3 has in average 82-86% methane and 5.1-10.4% carbon dioxide. Methane is purely thermogenic with no microbial origin.
7. Carbon dioxide originates from dolomite dissolution.
8. Hydrogen sulphide occurs at the annulus irregularly up to 10 mg/m³ gas. In the produced gas it is mostly <2 mg/m³ gas.
9. The soil gas samples contain CO₂ in the amount from 0,146 to 7.188%vol, the carbon isotopic composition δ¹³C-CO₂ ranges from -21.7 to -14.5‰.
10. Formation water in the Zar-3 reservoir is a brine of Na-Cl type with mineralization (TDS) 24230-26130 mg/L.
11. Formation water mineralization (TDS) is the highest in the underlying units of the crystalline and Paleozoics. The overburden caprock formations have water with decreasing upward mineralization, still similar to the main reservoir. Infiltration of fresh water is observed at maximum in the first kilometre from the surface.
12. It may be concluded, that the caprocks seal the reservoir at a sufficient level also for future CO₂ storage.

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Standards:

ČSN EN ISO 12185: Determination of density of liquids – by oscillating U-tube method and calculation of API gravity index

ČSN EN ISO 3405; ČSN EN ISO 4264: Determination of distillation characteristics at atmospheric pressure.

ČSN ISO 760: Determination of water content by KF method by volumetry.

ČSN EN ISO 2719: Procedure A, C - Determination of flash point – Pensky-Martens closed cup.

ČSN EN ISO 3104; ČSN ISO 2909: Determination of dynamic viscosity by falling-ball viscometer and calculation of kinematic viscosity and viscosity index .

ČSN EN 12634: Determination of acid value by potentiometry.

ČSN EN ISO 8754: Determination of elements by ED XRF.

ČSN EN ISO 20847: Determination of elements by ED XRF.

ČSN EN ISO 13032: Determination of elements by ED XRF.

ASTM D8252: Determination of elements by ED XRF.

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PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

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